

Drought : science, tools and trends

Takumi Therville
University of Antwerp

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Definition of drought

Droughts refer to periods of time with substantially below-average moisture conditions, usually covering large areas, during which limitations in water availability result in negative impacts for various components of natural systems and economic sectors.

IPCC 2021

What?

Droughts refer to periods of time with substantially below-average moisture conditions, usually covering large areas, during which **limitations in water availability** result in negative impacts for various components of natural systems and economic sectors.

IPCC 2021

When?

From a few days and weeks,

Through a few months,

to several years.

Droughts refer to **periods of time** with substantially below-average moisture conditions, usually covering large areas, during which limitations in water availability result in negative impacts for various components of natural systems and economic sectors.

IPCC 2021

When/where?

Droughts refer to periods of time with substantially **below-average moisture conditions**, usually covering large areas, during which limitations in water availability result in negative impacts for various components of natural systems and economic sectors.

IPCC 2021

Drought vs Aridity

Drought : temporary abnormally dry

Aridity : permanent* climate feature

Drought vs Aridity

Drought

Situation 2025-09-01 European drought observatory (EDO)

Aridity

(Zomer, R.J., Xu, J. & Trabucco, A, 2022)

What is drought

Droughts refer to periods of time with substantially below-average moisture conditions, usually covering large areas, during which limitations in water availability result in **negative impacts for various components of natural systems and economic sectors.**

IPCC 2021

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
 - a) Ecosystem impacts
 - b) Social impacts
 - c) Economic impacts
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Impacts of droughts

Vegetation stress and loss
(Powers et al., 2020)

Satellite images of drought
impact on vegetation cover
(Cappucci, 2022)

Ecosystem

Impacts of droughts

Wildfires (Littell et al., 2016; JRC 2023)

The Joint Research Centre: EU Science Hub

[Home](#) > [JRC news and updates](#) > The EU 2022 wildfire season was the second worst on

NEWS ANNOUNCEMENT | 2 May 2023 | Joint Research Centre | 3 min read

The EU 2022 wildfire season was the second worst on record

Ecosystem

Impacts of droughts

Every year, enough calories to feed the population of Germany are lost to droughts (World Bank 2017)

Social

Impacts of droughts

Number of reported disasters and deaths from 1970-2019 (WMO 2021)

Number of disasters
Total = 11 072

Number of deaths
Total = 2 064 929

Drought
 Extreme temperature
 Flood
 Landslide
 Storm
 Wildfire

Social

Impacts of droughts

Conflicts, social
unrest and
breakdown
(Lucchetti, 2017)

2017

Drought — a cause of riots

[Download PDF version](#)

Social

Im

cial

Impacts of droughts

Transportation and supply chain disruptions

Industrial and energetic water restrictions

The New York Times

European Heat Wave | What to Know | Maps | Wildfires | Paris Braces for the Future | Spain's Old Ways of Coping | Managing Extreme Heat

Europe's Scorching Summer Puts Unexpected Strain on Energy Supply

The dry summer has reduced hydropower in Norway, threatened nuclear reactors in France and crimped coal transport in Germany. And that's on top of Russian gas cuts.

Economic

What is drought?

Drought isn't just a lack of rain — it's a complex hazard, defined **relative to normal conditions**, with impacts that **ripple through** systems. And crucially — *no region is immune*.

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
- 3. The different types of droughts**
4. Drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Physical mechanisms

Physical mechanisms

Different drought types

Meteorological drought

- Rainfall deficit
- Water vapor deficit

Different drought types

Different drought types

Different drought types *(UNISDR, 2009)*

Different drought types

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
 - a) Detecting drought – drought indices : SPI
 - b) Other standardized indices
 - c) Online tools for drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Why do we need drought indices?

Data from Dumitrescu, A. et al. (2025)

Why do we need drought indices?

Why do we need drought indices?

Why do we need drought indices?

Drought Indices

Multi-scale	Works at different temporal scales
Comparable	Provides comparable values across climate regions
Interpretable	Easy to relate to observed impacts (thresholds, severity)
Accessible	Can be calculated from available data
Sensitive	Reacts clearly to water deficits

The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)

(McKee et al., 1993)

Raw precipitation data

Accumulate precipitations over a chosen period

Obtain probability of precipitation amount over chosen period

Transform into Standard normal

SPI : Standardized Precipitation Index

Multi-scale	Works at different temporal scales	✓
Comparable	Provides comparable values across climate regions	✓
Interpretable	Easy to relate to observed impacts (thresholds, severity)	
Accessible	Can be calculated from available data	✓
Sensitive	Reacts clearly to water deficits	

SPI drought definition

SPI range	Condition
$SPI \geq 2$	Extremely wet
$1.5 \geq SPI > 2$	Severely wet
$1 \geq SPI > 1.5$	Moderately wet
$1 > SPI > -1$	Normal
$-1 \geq SPI > -1.5$	Moderately dry
$-1.5 \geq SPI > -2$	Severely dry
$-2 \geq SPI$	Extremely dry

(Keyantash & National Center for Atmospheric Research Staff (Eds)., 2025)

SPI : Standardized Precipitation Index

Multi-scale	Works at different temporal scales	✓
Comparable	Provides comparable values across climate regions	✓
Interpretable	Easy to relate to observed impacts (thresholds, severity)	✓
Accessible	Can be calculated from available data	✓
Sensitive	Reacts clearly to water deficits	

Drought detection with run theory

SPI : Standardized Precipitation Index

Multi-scale	Works at different temporal scales	✓
Comparable	Provides comparable values across climate regions	✓
Interpretable	Easy to relate to observed impacts (thresholds, severity)	✓
Accessible	Can be calculated from available data	✓
Sensitive	Reacts clearly to water deficits	✓

SPEI

(Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010)

- Apply standardization process to

$$D = precip - PET$$
 where PET is the potential evapotranspiration
- Considers temperature's effect on the water cycle

Agricultural drought SSI

(Sheffield, J. & Wood, E.F., 2008)

- Apply standardization process to soil moisture
 - At a certain depth
 - In the total soil column
- Different plants use different soil moisture depths
- Data scarcity and model assumption dependent

Hydrological drought SRI and SGI

(Shukla, S. & A. W. Wood, 2008;
Bloomfield, J. P. & Marchant, B. P.,
2013)

- Apply standardization process to
 - Runoff
 - Groundwater level
- Data difficulties
- Highly localized process

Drought Monitoring in Practice: A 2022 Example

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

Sustainability Nexus Analytics, Informatics, and Data (AID) Programme

HOME ABOUT AID **MODULES**

<https://www.sustainabilityaid.net/drought>

Sustainability Nexus Analytics, Informatics, and Data (AID) Programme

HOME ABOUT AID **MODULES**

<https://www.sustainabilityaid.net/drought>

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

<https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/tumbo/edo/map/>

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

<https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/tumbo/gdo/map/>

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

Make Map | Make Graph | INFO

GET MAP LAYER

Visualization Layer ?
Raster

Variable ?
Type: Search Datasets
Climate & Hydrology
Dataset: ?
GPM - 11km - Daily
Variable: ?
Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)

Computation Resolution (Scale): ?
11000 m (1/10-deg)

Processing ?
Statistic (over day range): ?
No Statistic
Calculation: ?

<https://app.climateengine.org/climateEngine>

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

Table 1. Indicators and indices listed in this handbook

Meteorology	Page	Ease of use	Input parameters	Additional information
Aridity Anomaly Index (AAI)	11	Green	P, T, PET, ET	Operationally available for India
Deciles	11	Green	P	Easy to calculate; examples from Australia are useful
Keetch-Byram Drought Index (KBDI)	12	Green	P, T	Calculations are based upon the climate of the area of interest
Percent of Normal Precipitation	12	Green	P	Simple calculations
Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)	13	Green	P	Highlighted by the World Meteorological Organization as a starting point for meteorological drought monitoring
Weighted Anomaly Standardized Precipitation (WASP)	15	Green	P, T	Uses gridded data for monitoring drought in tropical regions
Aridity Index (AI)	15	Yellow	P, T	Can also be used in climate classifications
China Z Index (CZI)	16	Yellow	P	Intended to improve upon SPI data
Crop Moisture Index (CMI)	16	Yellow	P, T	Weekly values are required
Drought Area Index (DAI)	17	Yellow	P	Gives an indication of monsoon season performance
Drought Reconnaissance Index (DRI)	17	Yellow	P, T	Monthly temperature and precipitation are required
Effective Drought Index (EDI)	18	Yellow	P	Program available through direct contact with originator
Hydro-thermal Coefficient of Selyaninov (HTC)	19	Yellow	P, T	Easy calculations and several examples in the Russian Federation

<https://www.drought.gov/documents/handbook-drought-indicators-and-indices>

Online drought monitoring tools and resources

Index name: Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI).

Ease of use: Yellow.

Origins: Developed by Vicente-Serrano et al. at the Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología in Zaragoza, Spain.

Characteristics: As a relatively new drought index, SPEI uses the basis of SPI but includes a temperature component, allowing the index to account for the effect of temperature on drought development through a basic water balance calculation. SPEI has an intensity scale in which both positive and negative values are calculated, identifying wet and dry events. It can be calculated for time steps of as little as 1 month up to 48 months or more. Monthly updates allow it to be used operationally, and the longer the time series of data available, the more robust the results will be.

Input parameters: Monthly precipitation and temperature data. A serially complete record of data is required with no missing months.

Applications: With the same versatility as that of SPI, SPEI can be used to identify and monitor conditions associated with a variety of drought impacts.

Strengths: The inclusion of temperature along with precipitation data allows SPEI to account for the impact of temperature on a drought situation. The output is applicable for all climate regimes, with the results being comparable because they are standardized. With the use of temperature data, SPEI is an ideal index when looking at the impact of climate change in model output under various future scenarios.

Weaknesses: The requirement for a serially complete dataset for both temperature and precipitation may limit its use due to insufficient data being available. Being a monthly index, rapidly developing drought situations may not be identified quickly.

Resources: SPEI code is freely available and the calculations are also described in the literature, <http://sac.csic.es/spei/>.

Reference: Vicente-Serrano, S.M., S. Begueria and J.I. Lopez-Moreno, 2010: A multi-scalar drought index sensitive to global warming: the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index. *Journal of Climate*, 23:1696–1718.

<https://www.drought.gov/documents/handbook-drought-indicators-and-indices>

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
- 5. Drought trends**
 - a) Historical trends
 - b) Future trends
 - c) Future risk trends
6. Future perspectives

Trends of drought - historical

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI-12)

Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI-12)

Colour Significant trends
 XXXX Non-significant trends
 No data

Figure 11.17 in IPCC, 2021: Chapter 11. In: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

Trends of drought – future climate

We can also look at drought event characteristics...
like duration

Figure 2-4 a) from Tabari & Willem (2022)

Δ [mon/decade]

-4 -3 -2 -1 0 1 2 3 4

Trends of drought – future climate

We can also look at drought
event characteristics...
like duration or **frequency**

Figure 2-4 b) from Tabari & Willem (2022)

Impacts and risk (IPCC AR5)

Trends of drought – future risk

Figure 4 in Tabari, H. & Willems, P., 2023 : Sustainable development substantially reduces the risk of future drought impacts

Trends of drought – future risk

Figure 4 in Tabari, H. & Willems, P., 2023 : Sustainable development substantially reduces the risk of future drought impacts

Trends of drought – future risk in Romania

Moderate drought

Severe drought

Extreme drought

SSP1

SSP5

Figure 4 in Tabari, H. & Willems, P., 2023 : Sustainable development substantially reduces the risk of future drought impacts

Future risk

Figure 5 in Tabari, H. & Willems, P., 2023 : Sustainable development substantially reduces the risk of future drought impacts

Table of contents

1. What is drought?
2. Why study droughts?
3. The different types of droughts
4. Drought monitoring
5. Drought trends
6. Future perspectives

Future perspectives – drought types

- Flash drought
- Multivariate drought
- Socio-economic droughts
- ...

Future perspectives – risk and impact

- Risk framework
 - Exposure
 - Vulnerability
- Impacts often underestimated

Thank you for your attention !

University of Antwerp
M4S |
Modelling For Sustainability

Takumi Therville
Modelling for Sustainability (M4S)
University of Antwerp, Belgium
takumi.Therville@uantwerpen.be

References

- IPCC. 2021. Seneviratne, S.I., X. Zhang, M. Adnan, W. Badi, C. Dereczynski, A. Di Luca, S. Ghosh, I. Iskandar, J. Kossin, S. Lewis, F. Otto, I. Pinto, M. Satoh, S.M. Vicente-Serrano, M. Wehner, and B. Zhou, 2021: Weather and Climate Extreme Events in a Changing Climate. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*[Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 1513–1766, doi: 10.1017/9781009157896.013.
- FAO 2021. The impact of disasters and crises on agriculture and food security: 2021. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb3673en>
- UNDRR 2021. United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (2021). *GAR Special Report on Drought 2021: Summary for Policymakers*. Geneva.
- WMO 2019. WMO Atlas of Mortality and Economic Losses from Weather, Climate and Water Extremes (1970–2019). Geneva. <https://library.wmo.int/idurl/4/57564>
- World Bank 2017. Damania, Richard; Desbureaux, Sébastien; Hyland, Marie; Islam, Asif; Moore, Scott; Rodella, Aude-Sophie; Russ, Jason; Zaveri, Esha. 2017. *Uncharted Waters: The New Economics of Water Scarcity and Variability*. © World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/28096>
- IDMC 2022. Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (2022). *Global Report on Internal Displacement 2022*. Geneva.
- Littell, J. S., Peterson, D. L., Riley, K. L., Liu, Y., & Luce, C. H. (2016). A review of the relationships between drought and forest fire in the United States. *Global change biology*, 22(7), 2353–2369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13275>
- JRC 2023. The EU 2022 wildfire season was the second worst on record. (2023, May 2). The Joint Research Centre: EU Science Hub. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/jrc-news-and-updates/eu-2022-wildfire-season-was-second-worst-record-2023-05-02_en
- Stocker, B.D., Zscheischler, J., Keenan, T.F. *et al.* Drought impacts on terrestrial primary production underestimated by satellite monitoring. *Nat. Geosci.* **12**, 264–270 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0318-6>
- Cappucci, A. (2022, August 11) Extreme drought is gripping Europe, intensifying heat and fueling fires. The Washington Post. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/climate-environment/2022/08/11/europe-drought-heatwave-fires-climate/>
- Powers, J. S., Vargas G. G., Brodrribb, T. J., Schwartz, N. B., Pérez-Aviles, D., Smith-Martin, C. M., Becknell, J. M., Aureli, F., Blanco, R., Calderón-Morales, E., Calvo-Alvarado, J. C., Calvo-Obando, A. J., Chavarría, M. M., Carvajal-Vanegas, D., Jiménez-Rodríguez, C. D., Murillo Chacon, E., Schaffner, C. M., Werden, L. K., Xu, X., & Medvigy, D. (2020). A catastrophic tropical drought kills hydraulically vulnerable tree species. *Global change biology*, 26(5), 3122–3133. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15037>

References (cont.)

- Delacroix, G. (2022, August 15). Western Europe's wildlife is suffering from the drought. Le Monde.fr. https://www.lemonde.fr/en/environment/article/2022/08/15/western-europe-s-wildlife-is-suffering-from-the-drought_5993670_114.html
- Von der Brelie, G. (2022, October 20). Climate crisis: how beetles and fire are devouring European forests. Euro News. <https://www.euronews.com/2022/10/20/climate-crisis-how-beetles-and-fire-are-devouring-european-forests>
- Sanders, S. K. D., Van Kleunen, M., Allan, E., & Thakur, M. P. (2024). Effects of extreme drought on the invasion dynamics of by non-native plants. *Trends in Plant Science*, 30(3), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2024.10.009>
- Al-Aisae, M. M., Velazhahan, R., Nawaz, A., & Farooq, M. (2025). Morphological, Physiological, and Biochemical Impacts of Drought on Wheat-Pest-Pathogen Interactions. *Physiologia plantarum*, 177(4), e70364. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.70364>
- Lucchetti, J. (2017, September 15). Drought — a cause of riots. University of Geneva – Press release. <https://www.unige.ch/medias/en/2017/la-secheresse-source-demeutes>
- National Geographic. (2018, March 12). How Cape Town's Residents Are Surviving the Water Crisis—For Now | National Geographic [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XxZAqswJfL4>
- Alexandru, D. (2023, October 31). Drought monitoring in Romania [slides]. Meteo Romania. https://www.iawd.at/files/File/events/2023/Drought_Conference/DANIEL_ALEXANDRU.pdf
- Horowitz, J. (2022, August 18). Europe's Scorching Summer Puts Unexpected Strain on Energy Supply. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/08/18/world/europe/drought-heat-energy.html>
- Bevacqua, E., Rakovec, O., Schumacher, D.L. *et al.* Direct and lagged climate change effects intensified the 2022 European drought. *Nat. Geosci.* **17**, 1100–1107 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-024-01559-2>

References (cont. & end)

- United Nations, The United Nations World Water Development Report 2023: Partnerships and Cooperation for Water. UNESCO, Paris
- UNISDR, 2009. Drought Risk Reduction Framework and Practices: Contributing to the Implementation of the Hyogo Framework for Action. United Nations secretariat of the International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR), Geneva, Switzerland, 213 pp
- Dumitrescu, A., Micu, D., Guijarro, J. *et al.* Long-term homogenized air temperature and precipitation datasets in Romania, 1901–2023. *Sci Data* **12**, 1116 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-05371-4>
- McKee, T. B., N. J. Doesken, and J. Kliest, 1993: The relationship of drought frequency and duration to time scales. In *Proceedings of the 8th Conference of Applied Climatology, 17-22 January, Anaheim, CA*. American Meteorological Society, Boston, MA. 179-184.
- Keyantash, John & National Center for Atmospheric Research Staff (Eds). Last modified 2025-04-29 "The Climate Data Guide: Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)." Retrieved from <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/standardized-precipitation-index-spi> on 2025-09-03.
- Vicente-Serrano, S. M., S. Beguería, and J. I. López-Moreno, 2010: A Multiscalar Drought Index Sensitive to Global Warming: The Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index. *J. Climate*, **23**, 1696–1718, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JCLI2909.1>.
- Shukla, S., and A. W. Wood (2008), Use of a standardized runoff index for characterizing hydrologic drought, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 35, L02405, doi:10.1029/2007GL032487.
- Bloomfield, J. P. and Marchant, B. P.: Analysis of groundwater drought building on the standardised precipitation index approach, *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 17, 4769–4787, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-17-4769-2013>, 2013.
- Tabari, H., & Willems, P. (2022). Trivariate Analysis of Changes in Drought Characteristics in the CMIP6 Multimodel Ensemble at Global Warming Levels of 1.5°, 2°, and 3°C. *Journal of Climate*, 35(18), 5823-5837. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-21-0993.1>
- Tabari, H., Willems, P. Sustainable development substantially reduces the risk of future drought impacts. *Commun Earth Environ* **4**, 180 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00840-3>